

Results and Discussion

TG plot of the blue adsorbed derivative of 3A zeolite can be resolved easily into four parts indicating various thermochemical changes. These changes occur over distinguishable temperature limits. Kinetics of these thermal events can be evaluated from the rate of change in weight with time and computation of activation energies indicates the nature of the thermochemical processes. While non-linear plots were obtained for $g(\alpha)$ vs time for $n=1, 2$ and 3 , linear plots were obtained for $\ln[g(\alpha)/T^n]$ vs $1000/T$. The first major step of weight loss occurs between 293 and 693 K, attributed to dehydration, loss of ammonia and the desorption of the organic dye. Further dehydration occurs between 713 and 833 K followed by deammoniation, dehydroxylation and formation of oxide residue from 873 K. However, the zeolite remains stable. Collapse of the alumino-silicate structure occurs only after the residue after initial TG analysis upto 1273 K is further heated to eliminate residual water molecules. The brownish residue shows loss of weight of only 2.1% between 633 and 713. The presence of an oxide residue was found⁴ at 603 K in the investigation of the thermal behaviour of Cu(II)-Y zeolite. Similarly deammoniation of ammonium X zeolite showed loss of physical water at 373 K and ammonia dissociation from small pores at 448 K and from large pores between 453 and 623 K. For $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ -Y zeolite deammoniation took place at 70° higher than the $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ -X zeolite⁵. Dehydroxylation occurred for $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ -Y around 923 K. The thermal behaviour of the blue adsorbed derivative of 3A zeolite can thus be compared with the known behaviours of other zeolite samples.

The ir spectra of the new blue derivative exhibit prominent absorption bands at 3300, 1640 and 1000 cm^{-1} . A shoulder at 1440 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 1400 cm^{-1} indicate interaction of ammonia with Cu(II) cation. The ir spectra of the residue after heating to 1273 K exhibit only a weak peak at 3200 cm^{-1} and a broad and shallow peak between 1300 and 960 cm^{-1} . Heating eliminates both the physically adsorbed water and the $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ cation as indicated by the disappearance of bands at 1640 and 1400 cm^{-1} . X-ray diffraction studies of hydrated $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ -Mordenite⁶ revealed that deposition of amorphous alumina occurred in the pores as a result of heating. This was also indicated by shifts in the ir spectra in the framework region which showed that the crystal became more siliceous on heating. The present studies of thermal behaviour of the blue adsorbed derivative of 3A-zeolite indicate similar structural changes. Moreover, the prior adsorption of Fast Sulphon Black F dye on the zeolite prevents the expected complex formation reaction with the copper(II) cation in presence of ammonia. Interaction with ammonia leads to the formation of copper(II) amine complex as well as the $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ cation. Earlier work on ammonia adsorption on A-zeolites showed formation of two species, ammonia molecules hydrogen bonded to the

lattice oxygen or coordinated to the metal ion and $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ ions located on Bronsted sites⁷.

The d spacings and the intensities were obtained from the X-ray diffractograms (Fig. 2) with respect to CuK_α radiation of wavelength 1.5418 Å. These data indicate much variations. These differences in d spacings for Cu(II)-3A zeolite and the new blue derivative and its preheated form can be attributed to the presence of the interacted species in the blue derivative and the structural changes brought about by thermal events.

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Stability Constants of Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of Hexachlorophene

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HEXACHLOROPHENE, 2,2-methylene bis(3,4,6-trichlorophenol), has got much utility due to its antibacterial activity. Its solid chelates have been reported in literature^{1,2}. In continuation of our previous work³ on the stability of its complexes of metal ions, the proton ligand stability constants of hexachlorophene and stabilities of its complexes with Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} are reported at 25 and 45° with ionic strength 0.1 M and at 35° with ionic strengths 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M in alcohol-water system (1 : 1, v/v).

Experimental

The reagents were AnalaR. Deionised water was used for making all the solutions. Carbon dioxide free KOH (0.1 M) solution was used for potentiometric titrations. The solutions of metal ions were standardized to 0.01 M . Hexachlorophene was dissolved in absolute alcohol to prepare 0.05 M solution. 0.05 M HClO_4 was used. The ionic strength was maintained with 1.0 M NaClO_4 .

Systronics 322-1 pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes assembly was used and standardised with

standard buffers. The water thermostat was used to maintain the temperature 25 ± 0.1 , 35 ± 0.1 and $45 \pm 0.1^\circ$ during titrations. Bjerrum-Calvin^{4,5} pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶ was adopted for the study.

Results and Discussion

The values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated from the plots of pH vs the volume of alkali added. The shape of the titration curves shows the release of two protons in two steps. The values of $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ were obtained from the plots of the equations

$$\log K_1^H = pH + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \quad (\text{where } \bar{n}_A < 1) \quad (1)$$

$$\log K_2^H = pH + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A - 1}{2 - \bar{n}_A} \quad (\text{where } \bar{n}_A > 1) \quad (2)$$

These values are given in Table 1. In all the cases $\log K_1^H > \log K_2^H$. The proton-ligand stability constants decrease with the increase of ionic strength and rise of temperature.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF HEXACHLOROPHENE IN ALCOHOL-WATER MIXTURE (1 : 1, v/v)

Temp. °C	Ionic strength <i>M</i>	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$
25	0.10	12.06	5.40
	0.05	11.30	5.18
35	0.10	11.00	4.86
	0.20	9.80	4.58
45	0.10	10.52	4.82

In the study of stability constants of metal complexes the ratio of metal to ligand was kept 1 : 5 in order to allow for maximum coordination of ligand to metal ion. The formation curves were drawn between \bar{n} and pL . These curves at 35° and ionic strength 0.1 *M* are shown in Fig. 1. The value of \bar{n} does not go beyond 2 in all the complexes which

Fig. 1. Formation curves of metal-hexachlorophene complexes at 35° at ionic strength $\mu = 0.10 M$.

suggests the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The complex of metals, $M(II)$, ion with the ligand may be represented with the following structures.

Fig. 2. Structure of $M(II)$ complex.

The values of stability constants calculated by different methods⁷ are given in Table 2. The thermodynamic stability constants obtained by plotting $\log K_n$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ at 35° and extrapolating to zero ionic strength. These are given in Table 3.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF HEXACHLOROPHENE COMPLEXES IN ALCOHOL-WATER MIXTURE (1 : 1, v/v) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND IONIC STRENGTHS

Metal ion	Temp. °C	Ionic strength <i>M</i>	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Mn ²⁺	25	0.10	7.10	6.00	13.10
		0.05	6.10	5.26	11.96
	35	0.10	5.78	5.20	10.98
		0.20	4.52	3.81	8.95
Co ²⁺	45	0.10	5.46	4.62	10.08
		0.20	5.05	4.20	9.25
	25	0.10	7.81	5.40	13.71
		0.05	6.90	5.72	12.62
Ni ²⁺	45	0.10	6.40	5.28	11.68
		0.20	5.93	4.88	10.81
	25	0.10	8.40	6.62	15.02
		0.05	7.00	5.80	12.80
Cu ²⁺	45	0.10	6.56	5.32	11.88
		0.20	5.40	4.95	9.75
	25	0.10	5.98	5.02	11.00
		0.05	10.40	9.00	19.40
Cu ²⁺	35	0.10	9.30	8.21	17.51
		0.05	8.62	7.68	16.30
	45	0.10	7.90	6.90	13.50
		0.20	7.98	7.25	15.23

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS OF HEXACHLOROPHENE COMPLEXES AT 35° ($\mu = 0$)

Metal ion	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Mn ²⁺	7.40	6.45	13.85
Co ²⁺	8.72	7.20	15.92
Ni ²⁺	8.80	7.40	16.20
Cu ²⁺	11.42	10.30	21.72

The values show the decrease of stability of complexes with rise of temperature and increase of ionic strength. The observed order of stabilities of the complexes is $Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Mn^{II}$. The stabilities of the complexes follow the Irving-Williams⁸ order. The higher stability of these complexes may be due to the formation of ring structure. The chelating effect, therefore, is contributing towards the stability of these complexes.

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Reaction of Guanidine with 3-Formyl Chromones

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GHOSH *et al*¹ observed that reaction of 3-formyl chromone with guanidine carbonate (in 1 : 2 molar ratio) in ethanol or acetic acid yields 2-amino-5-hydroxy-5H-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-d]pyrimidine (A), while the reaction under similar conditions of 4-oxo-4H-[1]benzopyran-3-carboxylate (C) with guanidine carbonate yields 2-amino-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-d]pyrimidine-(4H)one (B).

Considering the susceptibility of γ -pyrone nucleus towards alkaline solution, these reactions are likely to follow a different path under basic conditions. 3-Formyl chromones prepared by Vilsmeier-Haack reaction²⁻⁵ on *o*-hydroxy acetophenones were therefore condensed with guanidine hydrochloride in alkaline medium and the products isolated and their structures determined.

There is a possibility of the formation of two different pyrimidines (Ia or II) when 3-formyl chromones are condensed with guanidine under basic conditions. In order to find out which one of these compounds is actually formed the following set of reactions was carried out.

The oximes of the isolated products were subjected to Beckmann rearrangement in presence of dimethylformamide and phosphorous oxychloride which yielded the corresponding benzoxazole derivatives (Ie-Xe). The oximeacetates swiftly cyclised in dry pyridine to the corresponding benzisoxazole derivatives (Id-Xd). It can therefore be safely concluded that when guanidine and 3-formyl chromones are condensed in basic medium there is a formation of 5-salicyloyl-2-amino-pyrimidines (Ia).

IR (KBr) of 5-salicyloyl-2-amino-pyrimidines (Ia-XIa) showed bands at 1640 (C=O), 3140 (phenolic OH), 3400 and 3300 cm^{-1} (asymmetric and symmetric stretch of $-\text{NH}_2$).

NMR (CDCl_3) of 5-(5'-ethyl-*o*-hydroxybenzoyl)-2-amino pyrimidine (XIIa) showed the following signals :

τ 1.2 (J = 7Hz 3H - CH_2CH_3), 2.6 (dd, J = 7Hz, 2H - CH_2CH_3), 5.7 (s, 2H - NH_2), 6.8-7.6 (m, 3H aromatic), 8.7 (d 2H, 4 and 6 - H of pyrimidine ring), 11.55 (s, 1H phenolic OH).

IR (KBr) of oximes (Ib-XIb) of 5-salicyloyl pyrimidines showed bands at 3150 (phenolic OH), 3600 (N-OH), 1660 (C=N), 3455 and 3290 cm^{-1} (asymmetric and symmetric stretch of $-\text{NH}_2$).

IR (KBr) of oxime acetates (Ic-Xc) showed bands at 3180 (phenolic OH), 3390 and 3180 (asymmetric and symmetric stretch of $-\text{NH}_2$), 1780 (N-OAc) and 1655 cm^{-1} (C=N).

IR (KBr) of benzisoxazoles (Id-Xd) showed bands at 3320 and 3140 (asymmetric and symmetric stretch of $-\text{NH}_2$), 808 cm^{-1} (benzisoxazole ring stretch).

TABLE I—SUBSTITUTED 5-SALICYLOYL-2-AMINOPYRIMIDINES (Ia-XIa) AND THE OXIMES (Ib-XIb)

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	Molecular formula
Ia	H	H	H	210 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂	Ib	H	H	H	200 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂
IIa	CH ₃	H	H	220 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	IIb	CH ₃	H	H	205 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂
IIIa	H	CH ₃	H	200 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	IIIb	H	CH ₃	H	187 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂
IVa	H	H	CH ₃	210 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	IVb	H	H	CH ₃	220 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂
Va	Cl	H	H	287 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Vb	H	H	Cl	226 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl
VIa	H	H	Cl	230 ^c	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	VIb	H	H	Br	220 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Br
VIIa	H	H	Br	240 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Br	VIIb	H	H	C ₂ H ₅	210 ^a	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂
VIIIa	CH ₃	H	Cl	240 ^c	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	VIIIb	CH ₃	H	Cl	242 ^b	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl
IXa	H	CH ₃	Cl	276 ^b	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	IXb	H	CH ₃	Cl	265 ^b	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl
Xa	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	238 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂	Xb	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	241 ^d	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂
XIa	Cl	H	Cl	260 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	XIb	Br	H	Br	271 ^e	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ Br
XIIa	H	H	C ₂ H ₅	183 ^a	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂						

All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

Crystallized from (a) alcohol, (b) acetic acid, (c) alcohol + acetic acid, (d) methanol, (e) dioxane.

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